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Highway Infrastructure Politics: Cold War Power, Culture, and the US Interstate Highway Abroad

ABSTRACT

This article examines the historical roots and impact of the United States (US) Interstate Highway System on global highway networks. The article utilizes primary sources from the National Archives and Records Administration in Maryland, as well as website publications and journal articles. The Bureau of Public Roads (BPR), the system's creators, had a profound influence on the development of highways across regions. Several case studies of selected European and Asian countries have been used to exemplify this. However, by providing a comprehensive understanding of the Interstate System's role in global highway history, this article asserts that the efforts of US Interstate Highway planners after World War II have reshaped highway systems abroad, using theories of modernization, soft power, and technology transfer to achieve this. This article contends that the US Interstate Highway was not only a domestic project but also an instrument of Cold War diplomacy. Thus, this article contributes significantly to our understanding of Cold War infrastructure, demonstrating how an infrastructural project can serve as a mechanism of transnational power relations (soft power), tracing highways as global tools of US power.

Keywords: Bureau of Public Roads, Interstate Highway, United States, Cold War, Technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Interstate Highway¹ infrastructure can be traced to the 19th century. The US government approved federal funding for the construction of the National Road² during this period. Under the leadership of President Thomas Jefferson (1801-1809), legislation was passed to establish a 60-foot-wide right-of-way for a 20-foot-wide highway. Following a struggle between the federal and state governments, roads were finally transferred to the state governments. This led to increased road development and a rise in vehicle popularity, which ultimately contributed to the establishment of the Interstate Highway System.³ However, it was not until the election of President Eisenhower in 1953 that the system became a top priority. In 1956, Eisenhower signed the Federal-Aid Highway Act, which shifted the focus of public works from social welfare policy to efficiency and economy. The Interstate Highway project was a significant part of this shift.⁴ BPR⁵ played a central role in translating this transformative concept of the Interstate Highway System into a reality in the US and abroad. During the Cold War, the US adopted diplomacy and technological transfer as strategies to extend the Interstate Highway System abroad. This paper argues that

¹ It is a controlled network of highways in the US. For more on this, see Federal Highway Administration, "History of the Interstate Highway System," *Federal Highway Administration, U.S. Department of Transportation*, August 8, 2023, <https://highways.dot.gov/highway-history/interstate-system/50th-anniversary/history-interstate-highway-system>

² It was **Macadam Road** that people used to travel on with **herds of animals and covered wagons**. Also see, Hall Jerome and Loretta Hall, "The Interstate Highway System: 50 Years of Perspective," *Institute of Transportation Engineers*, (2006)

³ Hall Jerome and Loretta Hall, "The Interstate Highway System: 50 Years of Perspective," *Institute of Transportation Engineers*, (2006): 1-2

⁴ Jason Scott Smith. *Building New Deal Liberalism: The Political Economy of Public Works, 1933-1956*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006: 232

⁵ For consistency in naming, the Bureau of Public Roads was used throughout the essay to avoid confusion. For more on name changes, see Federal Highway Administration. "About FHWA." *U.S. Department of Transportation*, last updated February 3, 2025, <https://highways.dot.gov/about/about-fhwa>, National Archives and Records Administration, "Records of the Bureau of Public Roads (Record Group 30), 1892-1972," *Guide to Federal Records*, accessed September 18, 2025, <https://www.archives.gov/research/guide-fed-records/groups/030.html>

the US Interstate Highway was not only a local project but also an instrument in Cold War diplomacy and technology transfer. This paper uses the frameworks of modernization theory and the geopolitics of development to illustrate how the US utilized road infrastructure projects as a form of soft power to secure allies, counter communist influence, and demonstrate technological superiority.⁶ By examining the case studies of selected European and Asian countries, this study illustrates how US highway planners influenced the global mobility regime. In doing this, the paper frames the highway as an infrastructure of power, diplomacy, and cultural transfer.

Scholarship on the Interstate Highway System has mainly been locally focused, primarily examining its domestic cultural, social, political, and environmental impacts. There is minimal emphasis on its role as a transnational phenomenon. Scholars have demonstrated the cultural and human dimensions of the Interstate Highway System. They show how it reshaped lives locally by illustrating how race, urban renewal, and federal power influenced infrastructural development. This scholarship is limited to national boundaries.⁷ Jason Smith and Frank Schippers have taken the argument abroad, demonstrating its transnational nature. Smith linked the New Deal's public works, including Truman's Point IV Program, to Cold War development policies abroad.⁸ Similarly, Frank Schippers, through a mobility history perspective, showed how the Interstate Highway idea was transferred to Europe and Asia during the reconstruction and integration era.⁹

Yet, a significant gap remains. Much scholarship has focused on the Interstate Highway, either locally or, in isolated cases, transnationally. Few works have extended to cover different continents. While historians of mobility and technology discuss technology transfer, the broader theoretical framework of modernization, soft power, and infrastructure as forms of politics has remained underutilized. The article draws on Nils Gilman and David Ekbladh's connection of developmental projects to Cold War statecraft, Joseph Nye's concepts of soft power, and Brian Larkin's cultural analysis of infrastructure, demonstrating how technical knowledge can be a source of power.¹⁰ Similarly, Bruce Seely and Frank Schipper have demonstrated how highway technical knowledge was transferred abroad with local adaptations.¹¹

This article advances the historiography by highlighting the Interstate Highways within these broader theoretical premises. It adopts multi-continental case studies and theories. The study demonstrates how highways, long studied domestically, must also be understood as global infrastructures of Cold War diplomacy and power. It is the first study to connect BPR's abroad programs across two continents to Cold War statecraft via soft-power infrastructure.

2. US BUREAU OF PUBLIC ROADS, COLD WAR INFRASTRUCTURAL POLITICS, AND THE CREATION OF HIGHWAYS ABROAD

2.1 Selected European Countries

In Europe, the US highway assistance of countries reveals how the BPR used reconstruction of war-torn countries to augment its organizational and Western identity logic. Germany exhibits symbolic reconstruction, Turkey undergoes strategic modernization, while Scandinavia becomes a marker of prosperity and Western identity.

⁶ Nils Gilman, *Mandarins of the Future: Modernization Theory in Cold War America* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2003); David Ekbladh, *The Great American Mission: Modernization and the Construction of an American World Order* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2010); Joseph S. Nye Jr., *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics* (New York: PublicAffairs, 2004); Brian Larkin, "The Politics and Poetics of Infrastructure," *Annual Review of Anthropology* 42 (2013); Bruce E. Seely, Donald E. Klingner, and Gary Klein, "'Push' and 'Pull' Factors in Technology Transfer: Moving American-Style Highway Engineering to Europe, 1945-1965," *Comparative Technology Transfer and Society* 2, no. 3 (2004); Frank Schipper, *Driving Europe: Building Europe on Roads in the Twentieth Century* (Amsterdam: Aksant, 2008).

⁷ Mark H Rose, and Raymond A Mohl. *Interstate: Highway Politics and Policy Since 1939* (version 3rd ed.). 3rd ed. Knoxville: University of Tennessee Press, 2012; Tom Lewis. *Divided Highways: Building the Interstate Highways, Transforming American Life* (version Updated edition.). Updated. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2013.

⁸ Jason Scott Smith. *Building New Deal Liberalism: The Political Economy of Public Works, 1933-1956*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006: 248-249

⁹ Frank Schipper. *Driving Europe: Building Europe on Roads in the Twentieth Century*. Technology and European History Series, 3. Amsterdam: Aksant, 2008: 28-33

¹⁰ Nils Gilman. *Mandarins of the Future: Modernization Theory in Cold War America*. United Kingdom: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2003; David Ekbladh, *The Great American Mission: Modernization and the Construction of an American World Order* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2010); Joseph S. Nye Jr., *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics* (New York: PublicAffairs, 2004); Brian Larkin, "The Politics and Poetics of Infrastructure," *Annual Review of Anthropology* 42 (2013): 327-43

¹¹ Seely, B. E. "'Push' and 'Pull' Factors in Technology Transfer: Moving American-Style Highway Engineering to Europe, 1945-1965." *Comparative Technology Transfer and Society* 2, no. 3 (2004); Frank Schipper. *Driving Europe: Building Europe on Roads in the Twentieth Century*. Technology and European History Series, 3. Amsterdam: Aksant, 2008: 28-33

After World War II, the BPR played a crucial role in Europe through the Marshall Plan¹². This program was launched to enhance the reputation of German highway infrastructure. Germany benefited well from BPR instructional programs on highway construction, engineering, and infrastructure development.¹³ Rather than transferring technical knowledge, the BPR initiative shows how infrastructural knowledge became a tool of geopolitical reconstruction. The US embedded its engineering practicality into the German project, forging both material improvements and symbolic ties that showed US alignment during the Cold War. The German engineers' participation in the BPR training sessions during the 1950s demonstrates not only the transfer of technical knowledge but also a reflection of post-war identity formation, which reinforces the transfer or integration of US economic and political systems.¹⁴ The BPR collaborated with the Mutual Security Agency¹⁵, despite initial resistance from the Germans, and the US insistence on regulating approaches to infrastructure as a condition for economic integration¹⁶ demonstrates its motives. The success of the integration illustrates how the highway, often viewed as a neutral space for mobility, became an instrument for projecting US technological authority and culture.

Turkey was also another European country that benefited from the US Interstate Highway Initiative through the Marshall Plan. In addition to this effort, the Economic Cooperation Administration (ECA) and the BPR assisted Turkey in developing its highway infrastructure system after World War II. For Turkey, the fundamental issue was essentially strategic. This initiative aimed to modernize Turkey's agricultural sector to integrate it into the global capitalist economy. However, the construction of highways was crucial because it enhanced access to agricultural raw materials, thereby stimulating economic growth.¹⁷ This was done to improve export mobility. A report by the BPR and the General Directorate of Highways of Turkey indicated how the National Defense of Turkey urged the US to provide aid worth \$100 million, with \$5 million allocated to develop the country's road infrastructure. While initial oversight by the US Army signals the militarized logic of the foreign assistance, the project was transferred to the BPR on December 4, 1947. This illustrates the US preference to wrap strategic priorities in the language of technical expertise.¹⁸ In this light, the subsequent negotiations in 1948 between the BPR and the Turkish Ministry of Public Works for technical support continued until 1958. The assistance offered ranged from cost projections and training for Turkish engineers to guidance on geography and road conditions, including staff deployment, with several positive effects. Ultimately, this was a means of embedding US practices into the very fabric of Turkish statecraft.¹⁹

The BPR also played a crucial role in the creation of the General Directorate within the Turkish Ministry of Public Works. The organization was structured, explicitly modeled after the US highway system. This highlights not only infrastructure but also institutional design, where modernization was to be achieved by adopting the US organizational template and professional culture. There were also recommendations for budgeting highway operations, designing modern roads and bridges, and procuring and maintaining equipment nationwide. The training program reached 5,000 equipment operators and mechanics, as well as 350 Turkish engineers and 152 personnel in administrative roles, extending beyond the transfer of skills and expertise to become part of the US infrastructure modernization project.²⁰

The US prioritized making vehicles a crucial element of its citizens' quality of life and the health of its economy before World War II. While several European nations developed their automotive industries during this period, none achieved the level of functionality that the US had.²¹ The US promoted automotive

¹² See this for further readings on the Marshall Plan: National Archives and Records Administration, "Marshall Plan (1948)," *Milestone Documents*, accessed September 18, 2025, <https://www.archives.gov/milestone-documents/marshall-plan>

¹³ National Archives, Records of the Bureau of Public Roads, R.G. 30. (1951–1955), Foreign Operations Correspondence 1939–1955, State Department to Germany—Office of the U.S. High Commissioner (June 1, 1954), (File 003.4 Germany (R), Box 3), National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD.; Seely, B. E. "'Push' and 'Pull' Factors in Technology Transfer: Moving American-Style Highway Engineering to Europe, 1945–1965." *Comparative Technology Transfer and Society* 2, no. 3 (2004): 237

¹⁴ *Ibid*

¹⁵ See: National Archives and Records Administration, *Records of the U.S. Foreign Assistance Agencies, 1948–1961: Records of the Mutual Security Agency (MSA)*, Record Group 469, entries relating to Germany, National Archives, <https://www.archives.gov/research/guide-fed-records/groups/469.html>

¹⁶ *Ibid*

¹⁷ F. Schipper. "Changing the Face of Europe: European Road Mobility during the Marshall Plan Years." *Journal of Transport History* 28, no. 2 (2007): 216

¹⁸ National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, 1947–1989, Box 12, Turkey Finance Reports, Bureau of Public Roads, Technical Assistance to the General Directorate of Highways of the Republic of Turkey, January 14, 1987, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD.

¹⁹ *Ibid*

²⁰ Frank. Schipper. "Changing the Face of Europe: European Road Mobility during the Marshall Plan Years." *Journal of Transport History* 28, no. 2 (2007): 172–216

²¹ Seely, B. E. "'Push' and 'Pull' Factors in Technology Transfer: Moving American-Style Highway Engineering to Europe, 1945–1965." *Comparative Technology Transfer and Society* 2, no. 3 (2004): 230

culture in Scandinavian countries, a deliberate effort. In Norway and Sweden, for example, the state's initiatives to expand its highways show how American-style motorization gained legitimacy through its association with modernization and prosperity. The Scandinavian government adopted these US practices of technical capacity but also signaled its participation in a particular ideology of mobility. In this sense, the Cold War serves as the backdrop to technical cooperation, where roads and traffic engineering become vehicles for cultivating shared Western models of citizenship, premised on mobility, consumption, and technological progress. Scandinavian engineers' enthusiastic adoption and subsequent export of these techniques indicate that technology transfer in this context was not a passive reception but an active re-articulation of US models into local settings. This reinforces US geopolitical objectives.²²

2.2 Selected Asian Countries

US infrastructure development in Asia reflects the extension of the Cold War strategy, which went beyond reconstruction to include alliance-making. The Japanese case demonstrates economic recovery and industrial logic, while Iran illustrates the tension between sovereignty and external influence. Cambodia and Jordan, on the other hand, highlight the institutional tools used to embed US influence.

Japan's highway development in the Cold War era was profoundly shaped by US political and economic hegemony. Japan adopted US engineering concepts, which highlighted not just technical modernization but also a mechanism for integrating Japan's recovery into the American postwar strategy. Through highway policy, US influence became embedded in Japan's economic infrastructure. This, however, strengthens the dependency and aligns Japanese growth with American commercial and security interests. Following World War II's devastation, the Japanese economy's recovery throughout the 1950s coincided with the US's involvement in the Korean War, which consciously prioritized rehabilitating Japan's transportation sector.²³ The US police defense force demanded Japanese cars, which further catalyzed an industrial shift. It revealed how Cold War exigencies transformed Japan from a devastated wartime state to a pivotal node in the American logistical and economic network. The US support for rebuilding Japan's highway network to improve vehicular mobility was not merely philanthropic but fundamental to securing a compliant, economically capable Cold War ally. The Japanese government's approval of amendments to road legislation in 1952 and 1953 led to the creation of a five-year plan to improve road infrastructure. This was closely tied to US advocacy and revealed an intentional US strategy to shape Japanese policy frameworks in accordance with American priorities.²⁴

In 1956, Dr. Ralph J. Watkins led a group of US professionals to Japan to advance dialogue on highway connectivity and financial evaluation methods. The intent behind these technical exchanges went beyond concerns about efficiency, as it served as a vector for propagating US models of transportation economics and cost-benefit analysis. Such encounters facilitated the internalization of US-style evaluation metrics, embedding profitability logics into Japan's infrastructure planning.²⁵ Also, the Japanese government's adoption of the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development's Road Investment Criteria and new highway laws reflects a deliberate shift toward institutionalizing supranational frameworks. These US-backed institutions dictated the terms of development, reinforcing American leverage over Japan's infrastructure priorities.²⁶ This illustrates how the US exerted significant influence in shaping the structures and trajectories of postwar Japan's highway expansion.

In Iran, US technical intervention was facilitated through the BPR, which began in 1957 and was funded by import-export bank loans. It was supplemented by the Iranian government when foreign capital was unavailable.²⁷ The purpose of constructing and maintaining highways was to serve as a vehicle for American technical orchestration. This was to integrate Iranian infrastructure into a global system shaped by US engineering standards and managerial acumen. During the 1964 fiscal year, for instance, BPR's projects facilitated the maintenance and asphalt paving of thousands of miles of Iranian roads, a testament not only to technical assistance but also to the transplantation of American models of state-led development.²⁸

²² Ibid, 230-231; Par Blomkvist, "Transferring Technology--Shaping Ideology: American Traffic Engineering and Commercial Interests in the Establishment of a Swedish Car Society, 1945-1965," *Technology and Culture* 44, no. 3 (2003): 504-527

²³ Frank Schipper. *Driving Europe*, 28-33

²⁴ Ibid, 28-33

²⁵ Ibid, 30

²⁶ Ibid, 30

²⁷ National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, 1947-1989, Box 21, The BPR Program in Iran, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD.

²⁸ Ibid

The composition of BPR staff in Iran demonstrates the ongoing negotiation of sovereignty within the donor-recipient relationship. Iran's reduction, expansion, and reconfiguration of BPR advisers reflected attempts to strike a balance between external expertise and national autonomy. This shows tensions inherent in transnational technical cooperation.²⁹ At times, contracts specified teams of US advisors, consolidating the importance of American influence in the formation of Iran's road-building administrative regime. The transferability of technical models was visible in equipment operation and upkeep. In 1974, meetings between the BPR and the Ministry of Roads and Transport aimed to deepen this relationship, providing guidance that extended from planning and research to safety and contract management.³⁰ This pattern marked a shift in Iranian infrastructural decision-making, where outside expertise became increasingly involved.

The US's extension of BPR's technical assistance to Cambodia, materialized in the construction of the Khmer American Friendship Highway, should be interpreted through both its material and symbolic dimensions. The highway's dedication ceremonies and commemorative inscriptions in 1959 marked a diplomatic exercise, showing American developmental benevolence.³¹ However, the words of President Eisenhower read: "This highway, built by the joint effort of Cambodia and the United States of America, is a symbol of the friendship of the peoples of our two countries and of our mutual desire for a free, independent, prosperous Cambodia."³² Such symbolism was, to a vast extent, central in legitimizing the US presence in Southeast Asia amid shifting geopolitical alliances. Beyond the material contributions, US engineers trained Cambodian personnel in operating heavy machinery, thereby demonstrating technological dependence and consolidating local reliance on external expertise and equipment.³³ This arrangement often translates to longer-term economic and institutional dependency.

Jordan's pursuit of US BPR assistance for highway infrastructure similarly reveals the agency of local actors within broader Cold War alignments. They sought out technical aid and integrated American road-building methodologies (such as the "A Road Program for Jordan" under the Point IV Program). Jordan used foreign expertise to transform its national landscape.³⁴ This illustrates a new form of dependency and external evaluation in public works governance. The construction of a new highway, including the 1954 construction of the Amman and Na'ur corridors, and targeted training of Jordanian engineers by US technicians, fostered a technocratic elite shaped by American infrastructural rationality. This shows the embedded international norms in the domestic project of nation-building.³⁵

3. POLITICAL MOTIVATIONS OF US INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT IN EUROPE AND ASIA

The approval of the Truman Doctrine in 1947³⁶ marked a significant turning point in US foreign policy. They prioritized addressing the challenges faced by impoverished nations while cultivating our long-term soft power agenda. This policy was situated at the intersection of Cold War global politics and the common phrase "Third World," which referred to countries struggling with political and economic instability.³⁷

The US saw the rise of communism as a global threat. This prompted the adoption of foreign aid programs, such as the Marshall Plan and the Point IV Program³⁸, as well as defense strategies to counter Soviet influence. As engineers had previously played a role in advancing US foreign policy objectives, it was under the Truman administration that they became integral components of US foreign policy. Their skills

²⁹ National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, 1947-1989, Box 21, The BPR Program in Iran, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD; National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, 1974, Advisory Technical Assistance Agreement between the Ministry of The Government of Iran and The United States of America Department of Transportation, Federal Highway Administration, Box 21, The BPR Program in Iran, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD.

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, Box 12, The American Aid Program in Cambodia: A Decade of Cooperation Turkey, 1951-1961, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD.

³² National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, Box 12, The American Aid Program in Cambodia: A Decade of Cooperation Turkey, 1951-1961, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD.

³³ Ibid

³⁴ National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, 1956, Annual Report of The Technical Service For Economic Development and Technical Service for Public Works, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD

³⁵ National Archives, RG 406 UD-05 1 International Programs Files, 1956, Annual Report of The Technical Service For Economic Development and Technical Service for Public Works, National Archives at College Park, College Park, MD

³⁶ See: U.S. Department of State, Office of the Historian, "The Truman Doctrine, 1947," *Milestones in the History of U.S. Foreign Relations, 1945-1952*, accessed September 18, 2025, <https://history.state.gov/milestones/1945-1952/truman-doctrine>

³⁷ Keith Aksel, "The Engineering Generation: The Story of the Technicians Who Enabled American Cold War Foreign Policy, 1945-1961" (PhD diss., University of Colorado, 2016), 2.

³⁸ For more information on this, see: Truman Library, *Background Essay on Point Four Program*, "International Aid Background," accessed September 18, 2025, https://www.trumanlibrary.gov/sites/default/files/InternationalAid_Background.pdf

and knowledge were leveraged to further US interests and goals in global politics.³⁹ The US extended aid to European and Asian countries to prevent the Soviet Union from offering any assistance to these war-torn regions and to win them over. Arthur Schlesinger states, “Our engineers can transform arid plains or poverty-stricken river valleys into wonderlands of vegetation and power...The Tennessee Valley Authority is a weapon which, if properly employed, might outbid all the social ruthlessness of the Communists for the people of Asia.”⁴⁰ Another reads, “the greatest danger to the security of the US is the possibility of economic collapse in western Europe and the consequent accession to power of communist elements.”⁴¹ And “the Marshall Plan succeeded in keeping Communists out of government.”⁴² Steil also noted the Marshall Plan in Europe “worked because the US aligned its actions with its interests and capacities in Europe, accepting the reality of a Russian sphere of influence into which it could not penetrate without sacrificing credibility and public support.”⁴³

The development of Interstate Highway infrastructure overseas during the Cold War was driven by the desire to restructure war-torn economies.⁴⁴ The Marshall Plan united legitimate humanitarian objectives with US political and economic ambitions. The E-Roads project envisioned connecting Europe with high-standard highways for trade and travel, a concept that gained momentum in the 1950s.⁴⁵

The allies’ formation was a justification for the US’s global forays into highway infrastructure abroad.⁴⁶ At this time, forming alliances was highly critical. This could be achieved by promoting highway networks and other forms of aid to other nations to win them over. This was a part of the historical power struggle between the two superpowers, the US and the Soviet Union. The infrastructural assistance was a case in which a country called on the US for aid to their highways, as in Jordan, as demonstrated above. Highways also symbolized US technological prowess and were promoted as models for emulation.

4. CONCLUSION

This article traced how the BPR disseminated information about US Interstate Highways to Europe and Asia during the Cold War era. Through programs for instruction, technical cooperation, and direct consultation, the BPR introduced American planning, design, and management paradigms that reorganized transportation networks worldwide. The Japanese, German, Turkish, Iranian, Cambodian, and Jordanian experiences illustrate how highways were more than just local connectivity; they were indeed tools for Cold War diplomacy and politico-economic competition.

The global expansion of US highway construction was driven by three primary motivations: efforts to contain communism, the revitalization of economies devastated by war, and the desire to assert US technological and cultural dominance. Highways exemplified the modernization philosophy of the era, serving as both functional instruments of economic development and symbolic representations of capitalist efficiency. Consequently, they evolved into what Joseph Nye refers to as a type of ‘soft power.’⁴⁷ An infrastructure that influenced others through demonstration rather than force.

By situating highways within the broader contexts of modernization theory, soft power, and technology transfer, the study advocates reevaluating the Cold War history of infrastructure beyond the nation-state framework. Highways examined domestically also need to be contextualized and understood as a global infrastructure of negotiation, alliance formation, and cultural exchange. This comparative, intercontinental research strategy highlights how American infrastructural projects reshaped landscapes and global power dynamics in the mid-twentieth century. It is essential to note that the concept of the Interstate Highway system was not only propagated by the BPR but also by other organizations, such as the International Road Federation and Yale University’s Bureau of Street Traffic Research, which were not discussed in this research. Further research could reveal how these organizations contributed to the dissemination of the US Interstate Highway system or infrastructure abroad.

³⁹ Keith Aksel, "The Engineering Generation, 30

⁴⁰ Jason Scott Smith. *Building New Deal Liberalism*, 250

⁴¹ Benn Steil, *The Marshall Plan: Dawn of the Cold War* (New York, NY: Simon & Schuster, 2018),12

⁴² *Ibid*,356

⁴³ *Ibid*,404

⁴⁴ Sarah T. Philip, "Acre Fit and Unfit: Conservation and Rural Rehabilitation in the New Deal Era" (PhD diss., Boston University, 2004), 330

⁴⁵ Seely, B. E. "'Push' and 'Pull' Factors in Technology Transfer: Moving American-Style Highway Engineering to Europe, 1945-1965." *Comparative Technology Transfer and Society* 2, no. 3 (2004): 232

⁴⁶ Sarah T. Philip, "Acre Fit and Unfit, 330

⁴⁷ Joseph S. Nye Jr., *Soft Power: The Means to Success in World Politics* (New York: PublicAffairs, 2004)

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